

Climate_CRICES

D.1.2.2 Stakeholder data utilization SWOT analysis

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1 Introduction

This report presents a comprehensive summary and analysis of the outcomes from partner meetings and local workshops held within the framework of the Climate_CRICES project. The primary objective is to consolidate insights gathered from diverse regional stakeholders, focusing on their experiences, challenges, and expectations regarding the use and integration of data for climate change adaptation and projection. By evaluating these discussions, the report aims to identify common gaps, weaknesses, and barriers, as well as opportunities and strengths, in the current practices of data utilization. The findings serve as the foundation for a SWOT analysis, providing a strategic overview of how data can be better harnessed to support more accurate climate change projections and informed decision-making processes across different governance levels and sectors.

Alongside the presentation of the Climate_CRICES project, including its objectives, current status, and accomplished results, the workshops primarily focused on addressing thematic areas established in advance by the consortium. These common themes (described in more detail in deliverable D.1.2.1), along with the subsequent preparation of a unified document by each partner organizing a workshop, enabled the development of a comprehensive SWOT analysis.

2 SWOT analysis

A strategic analysis was conducted to identify both helpful (positive) and harmful (negative) factors that impact the use of climate data in the creation and updating of adaptation policies in pilot areas. This analysis focuses on both internal and external factors (Figure 1). Internal factors, namely Strengths and Weaknesses, refer to aspects within the organization or stakeholder's control, representing elements that can be influenced or improved. These are factors that describe what the stakeholder can actively do to improve their situation. On the other hand, external factors, categorized as Opportunities and Threats, exist independently of the organization or stakeholder and cannot be directly influenced. These factors describe the broader environment in which the stakeholder operates.

	Positive factors	Negative factors
Internal factors	S TRENGTHS	W EAKNESSES
External factors	O PPORTUNITIES	T HREATS

Fig. 1: SWOT analysis matrix (source: own)

The goal of this strategic analysis is to assess the Strengths (S), Weaknesses (W), Opportunities (O), and Threats (T) related to the current and potential use of climate data for the development and enhancement of adaptation policies in the designated pilot areas. This analysis offers valuable insights for the next phases of the project and its further development. It is intended to clearly identify the needs and potential barriers related to the use of data, providing guidance for the design and functionality of the dashboard, as well as for ensuring its practical usability by different stakeholder groups. Furthermore, the findings will help to shape the next steps in supporting the development and implementation of effective climate adaptation policies, by addressing gaps in data accessibility, enhancing decision-making processes, and fostering better integration of data-driven approaches at local, regional, and national levels.

The SWOT analysis is the result of unifying the outputs from all project workshops. Between February and March 2025, a total of 8 workshops were held with relevant stakeholders in the partner regions. Workshops were attended by 37 organizers from project consortium and 99 stakeholders, representing a diverse range of mostly local and regional and authorities from public administrations, policy makers, NGOs and research institutions. The results are first elaborated in four separate chapters (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) and then summarized in and visualized in a table.

2.1 Strengths (Internal factors)

Within the Climate_CRICES project, it became evident that the participating regions and institutions possess **strong human capital and a growing interest** in using data to support climate adaptation planning. The workshops facilitated active knowledge exchange among experts from academia, research institutions, and local governments, laying a solid foundation for future collaboration.

“There are research institutes, universities in the wider region that can be involved in the climate change planning process and decision making.” (PP05 - Central-Danube Priority Area, Hungary, represented by Central Danube Development Agency Nonprofit Ltd.)

“Expressed interest from local authorities (Grad Zagreb) and involved stakeholders (Zavod za prostorno uređenje Grada Zagreba, Nastavni zavod za javno zdravstvo) in using new data and models related to climate activities.” (PP06 - The City of Zagreb region, Croatia, represented by North-West Croatia Regional Energy and Climate Agency)

Some regions **already operate or utilize data portals and dashboards** that provide visualized and easily interpretable data for decision-making. In addition to user-friendliness, the open-access nature of these tools makes them usable even for non-specialists.

“The Piedmont Environmental Agency, on behalf of the Piedmont Region, is responsible for the Piedmont Region Climate Change Portal, with promising synergies expected with the Climate_CRICES Dashboard.” (PP03 - Piedmont region, Italy, represented by Consortium for the Information System)

“In larger municipalities and in some counties, communication channels and cooperation have already been established to enable the processing of local data on climate change and the integration of climate change issues into local plans.” (PP05)

“The data portal (one of the stakeholders invited) service on the regional level was created recently, institutions are just getting to know it and getting used to the ability to query data and to work with it. Their goal is to make data accessible in a simpler form and available to the public so they can work with it. The creation of the data portal for the Liberec region is a significant step. Stakeholders are starting to get used to querying data and accessing it, which is a positive development for future use.” (PP09 - Liberecký region, Czechia, represented by Jan Evangelista Purkyně University in Ústí nad Labem)

International cooperation was also identified as a major asset, enabling the exchange of best practices and the harmonization of datasets across Central Europe. Furthermore, some regions have already **successfully integrated climate considerations into strategic documents**, which enhances institutional coordination.

“The extreme weather events of recent years (severe droughts of 2022 and 2024) have made all stakeholders in the region aware of the local risks of climate change and the need to prepare for them.” (PP05)

“Additionally, technical capacity within the Region has been strengthened, and structures specifically focused on climate-related matters are recently put in place, supporting the activities for developing and implementing adaptation strategies.” (LP01 + PP02 - Veneto region, Italy, represented by Veneto Region and ARPAV - Regional Agency for Environmental Protection and Prevention of Veneto)

“The regional planning association is considering all plans/concepts at federal and state level for the regional land use plan, e.g.: They are already including flood risk management into the land use plan.” (PP07 - Saxony region, Germany, represented by Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development)

“With the Saxonian adaptation strategy (2027) the development of adaptation strategies will be obligatory for Saxonian municipalities. This is an advantage compared with the German adaptation strategy for climate change 2024.” (PP07)

2.2 Weaknesses (Internal Factors)

A key challenge shared across regions is the **lack of sufficient human resources**, particularly in small municipalities, where there is **often no staff qualified to analyze or interpret climate-related data**. Many decision-makers lack awareness or understanding of the relevance and potential of climate data, limiting its practical application.

“The structure and the data content of the national level climate change related databases currently available in Hungary allow mainly specialists to interpret the data. Some participants working for municipalities have looked at the database but were not able to understand its structure and logic and thus developed a negative attitude towards climate change data in general.” (PP05)

“Many local authorities (Group 2) do not work with data at all and rely heavily on regional authorities. This gap in local data use and knowledge limits effective decision-making and planning (but it must be taken into account that in the territories of small self-governing units there is not enough capacity for working with data).” (PP09)

“Municipalities, especially smaller ones, lack adequate human resources for data-related work in general and climate change planning in particular. As a consequence, climate change data are usually not analysed and evaluated by municipal staff, which also results in low levels of data-based knowledge on climate change issues in most municipal offices.” (PP05)

Another major weakness is the **fragmentation and inconsistency of datasets**, coupled with limited regular updates and unclear methodologies. This reduces the usability of existing tools, especially when users are unable to import, export, or compare their own datasets.

“Competencies to link different datasets to set measures is missing in municipalities and also planning associations” (PP07).

“Challenges remain in making scientific knowledge easily digestible and accessible for decision-makers. Lack of centralized tools for climate data visualization, making it harder for stakeholders to apply insights in practice.” (PP04 - Burgenland region, Austria, represented by Research Burgenland GmbH)

“Data collected by the Environmental Agency (ARPAV) are not always easily accessible or user-friendly. Historical time series are often short, incomplete, or available in heterogeneous formats, making harmonization more difficult.” (LP01 + PP02)

“Many of the stakeholders do not have access to continuous and updated data, which affects the overall quality and timeliness of decisions. Data like satellite Landsat is not being fully utilized.” (PP09)

In some cases, there is also **no clear strategy for long-term funding** or sustainability of **the data platforms**, which threatens their future viability. Limited documentation and communication – due to resource constraints – further exacerbate these issues.

“No clear funding strategy was discussed for sustaining long-term data collection and analysis.” (PP04)

“No responsibility for data (licences); lack of data source monitoring (no information about the change of data source); lack of regularity in updating the data source and/or no data update at all; lack of awareness of where the data comes from.” (PP08 - Lower Silesian Voivodeship region, Poland, Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences)

2.3 Opportunities (External Factors)

The future development of technological tools – such as **centralized platforms** with user-customizable features (e.g., visualizations, regional comparisons, mobile access) – represents a **major opportunity for improving data-driven climate action**.

“Development of a centralized dashboard for climate data visualization could improve accessibility and usability for policymakers.” (PP04)

“Supporting stakeholders in linking datasets to set measures would be of great added value.” (PP07)

“The Data Portal has the potential to become a central tool for regional data sharing. The development of this portal could lead to better integration and access to data across institutions and departments, especially with further training and knowledge exchange.” (PP09)

There is also a strong potential for **deeper integration of data into public policy** and strategic documents, especially where legal obligations (e.g., Saxony’s 2027 adaptation strategy) and local climate action plans are already in place.

“Planning and strategy development are only one side of the coin. To support sustainable adaptation, it is important to include people with decision-making power, who might not be aware of their influence on climate change issues.” (PP07)

“Improvement of the policy (SECAP of the City of Zagreb) in various aspects, including more precisely defined measures, more specifically defined sectors in which measures are applied, and a higher quality, more detailed RVA analysis.” (PP06)

“The project continuation, developing the dashboard and the opportunity to influence the improvement of climate change adaptation strategies and policies in terms of measures, actions, and sectors.” (PP08)

EU and national funding programs are seen as **vital for ensuring continued data collection, visualization, and training**. Stakeholders also identified capacity-building efforts such as workshops and crash courses as key to improving climate literacy and enabling more effective use of data tools by a broader range of users.

“Future workshops could focus on training stakeholders on the effective use and communication of climate data. Knowledge-sharing initiatives could enhance policy implementation and stakeholder engagement.” (PP04)

“Future workshops focusing on practical use of data (e.g., dashboard visualization, ecosystem services) could increase stakeholders’ capacity to work with data. The inclusion of practical testing in these workshops is essential for increasing engagement.” (PP09)

2.4 Threats (External Factors)

A frequently mentioned risk is the **potential discontinuation of project funding**, which would lead to outdated dashboards and underutilized data resources. Without regular updates, these tools risk becoming obsolete.

“Lack of project continuation, which will cause the tool to become useless and outdated due to lack of data updates.” (PP08)

“Lack of understanding of the importance of comprehending climate change and responding to it.” (PP06)

“Lack of sustained funding could jeopardize long-term data collection and analysis efforts. Dependence on short-term project funding rather than structural financial support may limit the scalability of adaptation measures.” (PP04)

Data fragmentation, lack of collaboration between institutions, and **legal or technical barriers to accessing national databases** also pose significant threats.

“This lack of resources means that municipalities cannot employ the right specialists, buy data or develop plans of high quality. In addition to local authorities, the shortage of financial resources also affects research institutes and NGOs with a potential role in regional climate change research.” (PP05)

“The lack of communication between institutions and departments could lead to fragmented data, reducing its effectiveness and hindering the decision-making process.” (PP09)

“Risk of fragmented or inaccessible data sources leading to inefficiencies in adaptation planning.” (PP04)

Political and institutional shifts can disrupt climate-related initiatives, particularly when **competencies are unclear, or budgets are limited**. A further threat is the dependence on a small number of specialists; the departure of key experts could significantly hinder the continuity and quality of project-related work and knowledge retention.

“Insufficient involvement from key decision-makers may undermine the effectiveness of adaptation strategies. There are few experts, and there is a risk that they will change positions.” (PP03)

“An insufficient number of experts in local authorities and in general. Poor budget planning for climate policies and activities (adaptation and mitigation measures).” (PP06)

“Competences related to climate change adaptation strategies are fragmented, making coordination of relevant initiatives challenging.” (LP01 + PP02)

“Local governments have limited competences in many areas related to climate change and therefore are not interested in implementing high-cost, data-driven planning, as they cannot always benefit directly from the results.” (PP05)

3 Highlights

The workshops conducted across the partner regions highlighted several key common themes that reflect both the shared challenges and opportunities faced by the project consortium. These common themes were identified through collaborative discussions and have been integral to shaping the future direction of the Climate_CRICES project. The shared strengths include strong regional engagement, increasing awareness of data importance, and a growing commitment to visual dashboards. However, the consortium also faces common weaknesses such as limited capacity, fragmented data, and the technical limitations of current dashboards. On the opportunity side, there is significant potential for policy integration, further tool development, leveraging EU funding, and providing targeted stakeholder training. Conversely, the consortium faces shared threats, including data inconsistency, institutional fragmentation, and the challenge of securing long-term funding. These insights form the basis of a comprehensive SWOT analysis, which will guide the project's development moving forward.

Tab. 1: SWOT analysis - internal factors (source: own)

Internal factor	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
Human Resource and Stakeholder Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● S1 All regions demonstrated strong engagement from knowledgeable stakeholders, including experts from academia, research institutions, and local governments. ● S2 Local/regional institutions (e.g., Grad Zagreb, Liberec Regional Data Portal, Environmental Agency Piedmont) are increasingly engaged in climate planning. ● S3 There is growing interest and capacity for data work at the regional level, particularly in municipalities and counties that have previously accessed climate-related funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● W1 Limited human resource capacity is a widely shared issue, especially in small municipalities, to interpret or act on climate data. ● W2 Many decision-makers still lack awareness or understanding of climate-related data and its implications. ● W3 The lack of communication between institutions and departments could lead to inefficiency and hinder the decision-making process.
Data Platforms, Tools and Usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● S4 Most regions emphasized the value of existing dashboards and data portals, especially when they offer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - visualized data for decision-makers, - user-friendly interfaces, - open access and drill-down functionalities. ● S5 Dashboards (e.g., Climate_CRICES) are seen as practical tools even for non-specialists. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● W4 Recurrent concerns include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fragmented, non-harmonized datasets, - lack of regular updates and unclear methodologies, - technical language or design that limits usability (e.g., for local planners), - limited ability for stakeholders to import/export or compare their own datasets with dashboard data.

<p>Policy Integration and Institutional Cooperation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● S6 Some regions (e.g., Saxony, Piedmont, Liberec) already integrate climate considerations into local or regional strategies. ● S7 Strong international cooperation across Central Europe promotes the exchange of good practices and harmonized data use. 	
<p>Financial and Organizational Limitations</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● W5 Several workshops mentioned no clear strategy for long-term funding or sustainability of data platforms (in general). ● W6 Stakeholders expressed concerns that without continuous project funding, dashboards may become obsolete (Climate_CRICES Dashboard).

Tab. 2: SWOT analysis - external factors (source: own)

External factor	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>Technological Enhancements, Dashboard Development and Sustainability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● O1 Clear demand for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - centralized data platforms, - dashboards with training support, customization, mobile accessibility, and visual storytelling (e.g., via maps, time sliders, side-by-side comparison), - improvements in indicator representation and integration of socio-economic impacts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● T1 Fear of tool redundancy due to better-funded or more competitive alternatives being developed elsewhere.

<p>Policy and Strategic Alignment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 02 Legal obligations (e.g., Saxonian adaptation strategy 2027) and existing plans (e.g., SECAPs, state-level development strategies) offer opportunities to embed climate data deeper into governance. ● 03 Future updates and cooperation may align with EU-wide standards and frameworks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● T2 Changing political priorities or institutional restructuring can disrupt climate initiatives. ● T3 Unwillingness to adopt new tools or integrate climate concerns, especially where competences are unclear or financial resources limited.
<p>Funding and Partnerships</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 04 National and EU funding programs remain key to sustaining data efforts. ● 05 Many partners identified opportunities for deeper collaboration with meteorological institutes, NGOs, and advisory centers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● T4 A major concern across regions: lack of long-term project continuation could lead to outdated dashboards and underused data resources.
<p>Training and Awareness Raising</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 06 Stakeholders widely support further workshops and crash courses to raise climate literacy and enable better use of data tools. 	
<p>Data Quality, Fragmentation and Accessibility</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 07 Expanding collaboration with national or international institutions and data providers could improve data availability and sharing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● T5 Risk of fragmented, unverified, or inconsistent datasets, especially when institutions do not collaborate or update their systems. ● T6 Technical or legal barriers to accessing national-level data (e.g., in Hungary and Czech Republic). ● T7 Without sufficient data collection and monitoring, especially at the local level, decisions may be made based on incomplete or outdated information, limiting the

Dependence on Few Experts		<p>effectiveness of adaptation strategies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T8 Overreliance on a small group of specialists means that loss of key individuals could significantly hinder progress in several regions.
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Common Themes Across Regions

- Shared **strengths**: strong regional engagement, increasing data awareness, commitment to visual dashboards.
- Shared **weaknesses**: lack of capacity, fragmented data, dashboard limitations.
- Shared **opportunities**: policy integration, tool development, EU funding, and stakeholder training.
- Shared **threats**: data inconsistency, institutional fragmentation, lack of long-term funding.

Key Differences

- **Hungary (PP05) and Czech Republic (PP09)** emphasized the **gap between local and national levels** more strongly than others.
- **Germany (PP07)** provided the most detailed critique of dashboard functionalities and expressed **higher expectations** for technical features.
- **Poland (PP08)** uniquely mentioned **biodiversity and economic impact data gaps** as a dashboard weakness.

4 Conclusion

The stakeholder SWOT analysis conducted within the Climate_CRICES project has brought to light the diverse yet converging challenges and opportunities regional actors face in utilizing data for climate adaptation. It revealed a strong foundation of engaged institutions and an increasing interest in data-driven planning across Central Europe. However, significant weaknesses persist—especially related to limited human capacity, fragmented datasets, and lack of long-term funding strategies. These systemic gaps often hinder the effective use of data tools, particularly at the local level.

Encouragingly, the workshops also uncovered shared opportunities for growth. Legal obligations, policy alignment, and the demand for tailored training and centralized dashboards suggest fertile ground for improving data integration. The findings emphasize that advancing data utilization is not only a technical challenge but also an institutional one. Collaboration, stakeholder engagement, and capacity building are essential to overcoming existing barriers.

The insights gathered here will directly inform the next phases of the Climate_CRICES project, including the refinement of the dashboard and its supporting strategy. Ultimately, the analysis provides a strategic foundation for making climate data more accessible, reliable, and actionable—ensuring that future adaptation policies are grounded in evidence and tailored to the real needs of users.